

Major Themes in The Works of Chitra Bannerji Divakaruni

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Abstract: Chitra Bannerji Divakaruni is an Indo – American writer of great repute. She is a fine messenger of Diasporic sensibility felt by her during her migrant from India to America. She deals with the subject of Diasporic immigrant experience and highlighting the condition of women protagonist in her works who are living between two cultures. Her experience regarding the said theme occupies a great place in her works. Though several writers of Indian background like Sashidesh Pandey, Bharti Mukherji and Nayantara Sehgal, who somehow or with their personal reasons left India their motherland and stayed in the foreign land felt deeply the experience of immigrant experience. These writers have also works. But the experience shared by Chitra Bannerji Divakaruni in her works is unique and different in analysing and elaborating the things in her own way. Before going over the works of Chitra Bannerji what depict her to be a diasporic writer dealing with women who are living in two cultures; let us have a glimpse of the theme and definition.

Keywords: Emigrant Experience, Historical Dilemma, Patriarchal System.

Introduction

The people who migrate from one country to another with the hope to have the better employment opportunities happiness and to make their lives better; but on reaching another country they find a clash of their own culture to that of another country in the Diasporic community. This makes their own tradition and culture to forget and adopt new culture and tradition.

Sunita in Arranged Marriage

Sunita finds herself helpless what to do. Her own Indian culture makes her learn to serve her fathers-in-law and mother-in-law's together with other members younger or elder to serve them like a good Indian woman. She does not get chances in doing so far what she finds herself guilty. She wants to wear a Sari and follow all the traditions of India. This will not be allowed to do in a foreign land. She comes under the grip of nostalgia; so, she remembers her home, her parents and country very much. The tradition of that foreign

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land seems her queer and awesome. She becomes very impatient and reminds her home town again and again. The memory of her home town haunts her time and again: at other times I feel caught in a world where everything is frozen in place, like a glass paper weight. It is a world so small that if I were to stretch out my arms, I would touch its cold unyielding edges. I stand inside glass world, watching to scream. Then I'm ashamed. Mita, I tell myself; you are growing westernized. Back home you'd never have felt in is way. (P. 26) It is to be pertinent to mention here that Sunita has homesickness but her life in the foreign land goes on as an Indian woman. She wears clothes as an Indian woman, server her husband and worship the gods and celebrate the festivals as an Indian woman. She, therefore does not want leave the land. After sometime her husband murders a person at the store which becomes dangerous for her and her husband but even when she is not ready to leave the place. She tries to assimilate to the present condition which is quite different from consciousness: That's when I know I cannot go back. I don't know yet how I" ll manage, here in this new dangerous land. I only know I must. Because all over India at this very moment, widows in white series are bowing their veiled heads, serving tea to inflows. Doves with cut off wings. (P.33)

Tara in Desirable Daughters

Like Chitra Bannerji Divakaruni, Bharti Mukherjee is a name who has written parallel to Divakaruni in the respect of Divakaruni. She is Indian born American writer has depicted the condition of Tara Late, the character in her novel Desirable Daughters, similar to Sunita the central character in Arranged Marriage. Taralata has also nostalgic sense during the days she passes on the foreign land. Like her two sisters she is forced to leave India and to reside in the Diasporic community. She does not want to leave the land but she remembers the past life passed in Calcutta. Once a theft was done in the apartment Parvati her neighbours, she reminds the village deity, Shitala story of the olden days of Ballygunge park road. The three women of Calcutta is got caught in the grip where they are to choose an oppressive but known Indian tradition and liberating unknown fact of life. Tara reminds the city of Calcutta her own native place as: The city was Calcutta in the late fifties and sixties.... to be Calcutta Bhadra Lok, as we Bhattacharjee were was to share a tradition of leadership, of sensitivity of achievement, refinement and beauty that was the envy of the world. That is the legacy of the lost generation of Calcutta high society, a world into which we three sisters were born and from which we have made our separate exist. (Desirable Daughter, P.22)

Dimple in Wife

Bharti Mukherjee's characters have nostalgic sense in their heart and mind as the characters of Chitra Bannerji Divakaruni. All these characters are hanging between two cultures what to adopt and the rest to

leave. The characters like Sunita in Arranged Marriage and Taralata in Desirable daughters are hanging between the cultures; they don't know what to do. But these characters have sense of alienation and cross culture. Sunita is very much worried about her own country India as the Taralata. Nearly the condition of the both similar. Mukherjee's second novel wife is a psychological novel narrates the story of her migration from Calcutta to New York with her husband. She being a Bengali by birth cannot cultivate the transforming atmosphere inside of herself. Though she is middle class woman; but adjustment with the Diasporic family of three place as the novel is divided into three parts, the first is known Calcutta where all the ceremonies of marries held and where the childhood of the lady together with half of life passed; and the second part of the novel develops in America and the third one in Manhattan where both husband and wife live together by hiring an apartment. Amit and his wife Dimple reside in the hired apartment. The writer focuses upon the mental condition of Amit and his wife Dimple who are searching new identities on a new place. They are dislocated and displacement by some reasons. Dimple the heroine of the novel is very much suffered because of changing the identity, culture and religion. They have to face challenge in adjusting on a new place in the multicultural society of Diasporic community. They are immigrant, Dimple, therefore cannot go here and there to pass time because nobody is there familiar to her. Under such condition she passes most of her time in watching T.V. and Sleeping. She becomes full of pain when she comes to know that she is pregnant; but very soon she gets success into abort her child by skipping. She remembers that her son if born in India, Known as the child of India. What name she should give her to the child born on the foreign land. For the fear and shame, she does not give birth to the child but aborting is the final solution for her. Dimple cannot wear the effect of changing of the atmosphere and she comes under the grip of insomnia. Thus, the condition of Dimple is much pain able. She comes under the frustration because of living in an atmosphere in the Diasporic family where there is nobody to change the ideas. Under position of frustration, she murders her husband and later on commits suicide. This effect of Diasporic is seen in the novel.

Jyoti/Jasmine in Jasmine

Her most novel Jasmine depict the life of the character Jyoti, the heroine of the novel. Her identity of name is changed by her husband and called her from Jyoti to Jamine. Her original name is Jyoti; when she transformed on the foreign land she is known as Jasmine. If we change anybody is name: the identity of the person is changed automatically. Very interesting incident happens with Jyoti we she was a child a soothsayer comes and tells Jyoti that she would become widow at the age of 17yrs and that comes true. After the death of her husband; she runs away to America for better change; but on reaching there she is

raped by a brutal sea captain what she does not like. She plans to murder her and as a plan she gets success in murdering the captain. Due to dislocation she works like a man which does not suit to her personality. Jasmine passes from one situation to another to get comfort but what she was searching nowhere that. Jasmine suffers physically as well as mentally turmoil and torture on the foreign land. She does not get rest anywhere. After sometime she gets under the psychological pain changes of culture and life.

Ashima & Gogol in The Namesake

Like Bharti Mukherjee and Chitra Bannerjee Divakaruni, Jhumpa Lahiri is also the writer of two cultures effect and Diasporic sense in her works. All these writers have made a neigh in the field of Diasporic sense and sensibility in the reason they have also rooted up from their own origin and went to another land where they faced the problems and issues; through the characters they have created tell the pains and sufferings of these writers as a Diasporic. These writers, when lift their own mother land felt the feeling of displacement, alienation and nostalgic sense what they could brought in light through their characters which are their mouth speakers. Jhuma Lahiri is also one of the Diasporic writers whose novel *The Namesake* depict the condition of Ashima Ganguli. The novel focuses on cross cultural tale of a Hindu Bengali family who travels to booster. The story has gone to narrate the family's tradition bound and deep-rooted life in Calcutta and travel to America. We fine the character's name Ashok and Ashima who feels the jolt of the changing of place from India (Calcutta) to America (Boston). In this work we have the protagonist's name Gopal Ganguli coming from the second generation is very much suffered to find his particular name and identity. He faces difficulties in naming him and far that he struggles hard in the Diasporic community. He tires his best to adjust in the family where is alone and all alone and for his own self-definition he is ready to adjust in the family where and ready to leave his old traditional named. But he will not forget the memory of the past name and life. He thinks by changing his name, the Diasporic community will accept him. But he will not forget India to America suffers some kind of Diasporic difficulties. Being a foreigner a short of lifelong pregnancy A perpetual wait, a constant burden a condition feeling out of shorts. It is ordinary life only to discover a continuous feeling out shorts. It is an-going responsibility, a parenthesis in what had once been ordinary life only to discover that previous life was vanished replaced by something more complicated and demanding like pregnancy being a foreigner Ashima believes is something that elicit the same curiosity from strangers the same combination (*The Namesake*, PP. 49-50) Those people get caught under the two world the problem arises out what tro choose and what to leave out: people today, who go to foreign land cannot assimilate the culture that is different to their own motherland. What happens to the character of

Chitra Bannerji Divakaruni, Jhumpa Lahiri and Bharti Mukherjee generally happens with the same public person.

Divakaruni's Broader Themes in Arranged Marriage

To maintain the old human values reaching on a new. Place becomes the cause of mental conflict. Under such condition a man comes under dilemma what to do and what not to do. It is very difficult for one to run parallel both the cultures together. And on the foreign land if one practices one's own culture; he will not see with society of Diasporic community and very soon he will be out. Chitra Bannerjee Divakaruni born in India and at the age of 19 years in the year 1976 notice the cruelty of whites against blacks who were expatriate. She is very much careful about rootlessness and discrimination, alienation and abuses what she herself noticed in the foreign land. Her earlier work Arranged Marriage is the fine example of expressing the ill condition of Indian woman expatriate to America, how Americans behave and their intention towards these women have been highlighted. Bannerjee is the first writer who is an eye witness to notice the ill-condition of immigrant women what she has brought in light in her short story work Arranged Marriage. Divakaruni highlights the problem of identity, isolation, alienation and non-communication which cause a serious problem for Indians. She has established herself a reputed writer writing on a wide range of themes relating to Diasporic. Divakaruni feels pain and suffering when she sees the ill-condition of her own country people and says as: Expatriate have powerful and poignant experiences when they live away for their original culture and this becomes home and never white and then you can't really go back and he quite at home there either. (Divakaruni profile by Arthur J. Paris P.3) Diaspora happens when one is away from one's country; in the globalization age it is very common to go from one country to another for different reasons. In reaching such a place a person feels alienated due to not knowing language, culture, behaviour another component for that he could not assimilate to others which causes non-communication and setting up behaviour for these reasons one is left behind.

Theoretical Perspectives on Diaspora

Uma Parmeswaran a noted Indo-Canadian writer has highlighted the Diasporic consciousness as follows: The first is nostalgic for the homeland, felt behind with fear in strange land. The second is a phase in which one is so busy in adjusting to the new environment that there is little creative output. The third phase is shaping of Diaspora existence by involving themselves in ethno-culture issues. The fourth is when they have arrived and started participating in the larger world of politics and national issues. (Uma, P.108) The next story we have in Arranged Marriage is Silver Pavements, Golden Roofs depicts the condition of Jayanti

faces dilemma of an immigrant while she travels from Calcutta to America as migrant; praises her past life and memories the things which make her restless. While she is on the foreign land she does not like the system of Chicago what she rejects thoroughly. Her main object is to imbibe her own culture even while living in Chicago. She finds herself alienated and does not feel happy as nobody is there to set up communication with her and asks her how are you. She fully faces the role of Diasporic community living in Chicago. She has nostalgic sense where she is caught in the world from whence, she could never get out: My monogrammed leather cases are an embarrassment in this household. I push them under the bed in the tiny room I am to occupy – it is the same size as my bathroom at home. (Arranged Marriage, 44) Chitra Bannerjee Divakaruni, daughter of the second generation of poet, novelist and short story writer depicts the modern man's nostalgic, homesickness, identity crises on the foreign land. She has depicted when the two cultures are different how can they similarly be and become one. She is the pioneer in the field of depicting the painful anguish of Diasporic identity and the sense of alienation in her work Arranged Marriage. In her story Silver Pavements, Golden Roofs she has expressed Jayanti who comes on the foreign land in search of golden opportunity after her husband's death but she finds her opposite to her dreams. Her bitter experience and anguish for the future becomes a question mark upon her dreams. She recalls her olden days with playing boys shouting at her and Pratima about with her racist slurs and attacked them with the fistful of slush; Jayanti who was proud to be an upper class Indian questioned her relation to American race categorization and her entire perception of her own race is thrown into question after this incident: Now the others take up the word, chanting it in high singsong voices that have not broken yet, nigger, until I want to scream or weep or laugh because can't they see that I am not black at all but an Indian girl of good family? (P.51)

Conclusion

The conflict of culture between countries, alienation, nostalgic ruin the career of woman who go on the foreign land to fulfil their dreams, to earn money to make their lives colourful on the other hand the memories of the past haunt them time and again; so, their existence on the foreign land a question mark. Whether they would continue or leave for that is uncertainties. These women are passing their day under uncertainties.

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Citation in APA 7th Edition:

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